

Lipid Profile among Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease: A Cross Sectional Study in a Teaching Hospital of Tripura

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Abstract

Introduction: Chronic Kidney disease (CKD) is a condition that causes damage to the kidney or its gradual impairment involving the loss of glomerular and tubular function that lasts longer than three months. Dyslipidemia is a well-established risk factor for CVD. With an ever increasing CKD burden worldwide, providing treatments for modifiable risk factors, like dyslipidemia, becomes an essential component for improving outcomes. Therefore it is important to screen all patients with CKD for dyslipidemia and treat them as they are considered a very high risk group for CVD.

Materials and Methods: This study is a single centre observational study conducted in the Dept. of General Medicine, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital for 1- and ½ years study periods. 226 patients are studied who met the inclusion criteria following assessment of Serum Creatinine, Serum Urea, fasting Serum lipid Profiles (S. Cholesterol, S. Triglyceride, S. HDL, S. VLDL, S. LDL) ECG, Thyroid profile were done. GFR was estimated for each patient using the CKD-EPI equation. Mean values were obtained for LDL, HDL, TGL & Total cholesterol VLDL separately. Then standard deviations were calculated for each category of observations. P value of <0.05 was considered significant. To study the correlation between stages of CKD and lipid profiles Pearson correlation coefficient was used.

Results: In our study, most common lipid abnormalities found were Low HDL levels and Hypertriglyceridemia, Hypercholesterolemia, High LDL and VLDL levels were in decreasing order respectively. 84% of total study population the mean HDL cholesterol is significantly decreased and negative correlation is found between CKD stages and HDL level. 70.3% of study populations were having high triglycerides levels and positive correlation is found between CKD stages and triglycerides level. LDL level, total cholesterol, VLDL levels were elevated in 44.6%, 44.2%, 15.9% of total study population respectively and Positive correlation were found between CKD stages and their levels.

Conclusion: HDL level was lower and Triglycerides, LDL, Total cholesterol and VLDL levels were higher in the study population. Predominant lipid abnormalities were reduced HDL levels and elevated Triglycerides. Triglycerides, LDL, Total Cholesterol and VLDL were showing positive correlation as CKD stages increases there is increase of mean lipid profile values. There was a negative correlation between serum HDL level and GFR levels which was statistically significant.

Keywords: Lipid Profile, Chronic Kidney Disease, Cross Sectional Study.

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease [CKD] is associated with specific abnormalities in the lipoprotein metabolism both in the early and in the advanced

stages of chronic renal failure. It has been suggested that the renal dyslipoproteinaemia of renal insufficiency contributes to the progression of

glomerular and tubular lesions, with subsequent deterioration of renal function.

Regardless of age, Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a major cause of mortality and morbidity in patients with mild to moderate CKD [4]. CKD is a global health problem. In the United States Prevalence of CKD is increasing and affects about 19 million Americans. In the last decade United States has seen a 30% increase in patients suffering from CKD [5]. Due to the absence of a renal registry, in the Indian population the exact disease burden of CKD cannot be assessed accurately. In India due to chronic diseases the projected number of deaths will increase from 3.78 million in 1990 (40.4% of all deaths) to an expected 7.63 million in 2020 (66.7% of all deaths) [6].

Over the past few decades, it was accepted that CKD is related with a high mortality rate and accelerated CVD [7]. The prevalence of clinical coronary heart disease is 40% in which CVD mortality is 10 to 30 times higher compared to the general population of the same gender, age and race [8].

Indian studies on lipid profile abnormalities in chronic renal failure (CRF) have varied from no abnormalities at all to significant abnormality (Hypertriglyceridemia and reduced HDL) as described in the Western literature. The study by B Shah, S Nair, demonstrates that CRF is commonly accompanied by lipid abnormality in the form of Hypertriglyceridemia. [9] The study by Sumathi M.E, Manjunath M Tempad showed serum TGL, TC, HDL-C, have significantly increased in conservatively managed patients than in Haemodialysis patients. [10]

Since hyperlipidemia can be modulated by therapeutic intervention, it is worthwhile to study and compare lipid profile abnormalities in CKD patients. Indian studies on lipid abnormalities in CKD have not been consistent. Sharma and Kunde found no hyperlipidemia, whereas Gupta and Das observed hypertriglyceridemia and reduced high-density lipoprotein (HDL) levels in CKD patients as in western countries. In view of inconsistency and limited evidence, it was decided to study the lipid profile in our patients with CKD. Also there are reports available regarding accelerated atherosclerosis in chronic kidney disease due to altered lipid metabolism. In recent years, the levels of high-density lipoproteins have gained importance in view of the fact that increasing reports are available incriminating decreased HDL levels as one of risk factors for cardiovascular disease. Therefore it is important to screen all patients with CKD for dyslipidemia and treat them as they are considered a very high risk group for CVD.

Since hyperlipidemias become more pronounced as renal failure advances and can be modulated by therapeutic intervention it is worthwhile to study and compare lipid profile abnormalities in renal failure patients on different modes of management. Hence a cross sectional study was taken up, to study the lipid profile in patients of chronic renal failure on conservative management and on regular hemodialysis.

Aim

Evaluation of pattern of lipid profile in chronic kidney disease patients.

Objectives

1. To estimate the pattern of lipid profile in patients with chronic kidney disease.
2. To study the correlation of lipid profile with stages of chronic kidney disease.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Observational study

Study Type: Cross sectional study

Study Setting: This study will be conducted in the Dept. of Gen. Medicine, Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital.

Study Period: 1 and ½ years (Tuesday, 1 June 2021 –Wednesday, 30 November 2022)

Study Population: All diagnosed patients of CKD

Sample Size: The study subjects will be enrolled from Agartala Govt. Medical College and GBP Hospital during the study period. To calculate the sample size, the Kish and Leslie formula of 1965 for cross sectional studies was used.

- $N = Z_{\alpha/2} \times P (1-P) / L^2$
- $N =$ Sample size; $p =$ Prevalance; $q = (1-p)$; where:
- $Z_{\alpha/2}$ Standard normal deviate at 5% level of significance (95% CI) is 1.96
- $P =$ Prevalence of dyslipidemia in CKD patients = 82% [11]
- $L =$ Margin of error at 5%

Sample size (N) = $1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.82 [1-0.82] / (0.05)^2 = 226$

Sampling Technique: All consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients between the age group of 15 and 85 years with established CKD.
2. Patients with CKD with stage I-V disease.
3. Established renal failure was ensured by radiological evidence or biochemical evidence for >3 months
4. Patient who have given written informed consent for this study.

5. Patients who were on conservative or dialysis treatment for CKD.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with acute renal failure and nephrotic syndrome
2. Those who are on drugs affecting lipid metabolism such as β -blockers, statins, and OCPs.
3. Female patients who were pregnant
4. Patients with end stage renal disease treated with renal replacement therapy in the form of renal transplantation.

Methodology

Patients of known chronic kidney disease who are admitted in Medicine ward and attending nephrology clinic at Agartala Government Medical College and GB Pant Hospital will be subjected for this study. Informed consent will be obtained after informing the study subjects the details of the procedure. After obtaining the informed consent from the subject, he/she will be included in the study. History regarding symptoms and duration of the kidney disease, hypertension, diabetes, smoking, alcoholism, drug intake and treatment were elicited. A detailed clinical examination was performed in all patients including Height and Weight. After detailed history, being investigated, data were collected on Demographic factors (age, gender) serum Urea, Creatinine, CRP and Serum lipid profile, abdominal ultra-sonogram and Electrocardiogram, thyroid profiles, Serum lipid

profile (S. Cholesterol S. Triglyceride S.HDL S.VLDL S.LDL) were done for all patients.

After 12 hours of overnight fasting blood sample was taken for lipid profile from patients and for TSH levels from patients. GFR was estimated for each patient using the CKD-EPI equation. CKD stages were defined based on the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) Clinical Practice classification [12]: stage 3, eGFR 30–59 ml/min; stage 4, eGFR 15–29 ml/min and stage 5, eGFR < 15 ml/min. In this study, stage 3 will be referred to as early stage of CKD and stages 4 and 5 as advanced stages.

Statistical Methods

Mean values were obtained for LDL, HDL, TGL & Total cholesterol VLDL separately. Then standard deviations were calculated for each category of observations for study population. Student's T test was performed & T value was obtained. P value from T value was calculated. P value of <0.05 was considered significant.

To study the correlation between stages of CKD and lipid profiles Pearson correlation coefficient was used. The correlation coefficient can range from -1 to +1, with -1 indicating a perfect negative correlation, +1 indicating a perfect positive correlation, and 0 indicating no correlation at all.

Results and Analysis

Total 226 patients with chronic kidney diseases were included in the study.

Table 1: Lab parameter (Lipid profile + KFT + Serum electrolytes) (N=226)

Lab parameter		Mean \pm SD	Abnormality (%)
Lipid profile	Total cholesterol	195.93 \pm 25.09	100 (44.2)
	Serum triglycerides	156.61 \pm 31.65	159 (70.3)
	LDL	123.21 \pm 23.31	101 (44.6)
	HDL	35.73 \pm 8.38	190 (84.0)
	VLDL	24.83 \pm 11.92	36 (15.9)
KFT	Serum urea	89.54 \pm 34.46	156 (69.0)
	Serum creatinine	2.95 \pm 1.73	105 (46.4)
	eGFR	27.78 \pm 13.61	226 (100)
Serum electrolytes	Serum K ⁺	5.08 \pm 0.90	35 (15.4)
	Serum Na ⁺	141.24 \pm 7.11	142 (62.8)
Thyroid profile	TSH	4.71 \pm 1.18	123 (54.4)

Table 2: GFR category classification (N=226)

GFR class	Frequency	Percent
<15 GFR	50	22.2
15-29 GFR	74	32.7
30-59 GFR	98	43.3
60-89 GFR	4	1.8

Table 3: Lipid profile (N=226)

Lipid profile	Abnormal n (%)
Total cholesterol	100 (44.2)
Triglycerides	159 (70.3)

Low density lipoproteins (LDL)	101 (44.6)
High density lipoproteins (HDL)	190 (84.0)
Very Low density lipoproteins (VLDL)	36 (15.9)

Table 4: ECG changes (N=226)

ECG changes	Frequency	Percent
AF	2	0.8
LONG QT	1	0.4
LVH	84	37.1
LVH with strain	13	5.7
Normal	58	25.6
Sinus Tachycardia	6	2.6
ST↓L1, AVL	13	5.7
ST↓L1, AVL, V1-V3	4	1.7
T↓L2, aVF, V4-V6	6	2.6
T↓L2, aVL, V5-V6	4	1.7
T↓ V1-V3	15	6.6
Tall T, V1-5	20	8.8

Figure 1: ECG changes in CKD patients (N=226)**Table 5: Correlation CKD stages and lipid profile (N=226)**

	Correlation	CKD stages	TC	TGL	LDL	HDL	VLDL
CKD stages	Pearson Correlation	1	0.271	0.189	0.192	-0.098	0.215
	Sig. (2-tailed) – p value		0.000	0.004	0.004	0.040	0.001
	N	226	226	226	226	226	226

Above table shows correlation between CKD stages and lipid profile parameters where TC TGL, LDL, and VLDL were showing positive correlation as CKD stages increases by 1 stage (from stage 2 to 3) there is increase of mean lipid profile values by 0.271 for TC, 0.189 for TGL, 0.192 for LDL, 0.215

for VLDL and where 0.098 decrease in HDL value suggestive of negative correlation of HDL with CKD stages and all the changes or differences in values found to be statistically significant with a p value of 0.000, 0.004, 0.004, 0.001 and 0.040 respectively.

Table 6: Mean comparison of lipid profile with stages of CKD (N=226)

CKD stages	N	Mean	SD	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		P value	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
TC	2	4	163.50	19.416	132.60	194.40	0.000
	3a	36	191.19	16.372	185.65	196.73	
	3b	60	191.18	22.926	185.36	197.00	
	4	76	195.87	27.202	189.70	202.04	
	5	50	207.92	25.055	200.80	215.04	
TGL	2	4	106.75	32.999	54.24	159.26	0.002
	3a	36	154.64	27.584	145.31	163.97	
	3b	60	154.23	30.481	146.49	161.97	
LDL	4	76	154.97	34.169	147.22	162.73	0.002
	5	50	167.48	27.348	159.71	175.25	
	2	4	86.75	24.459	47.83	125.67	
	3a	36	122.69	18.430	116.46	128.93	

	3b	60	120.16	21.168	114.79	125.54	
	4	76	122.49	24.669	116.89	128.09	
	5	50	131.36	23.645	124.64	138.08	
HDL	2	4	38.25	6.652	31.06	35.94	0.014
	3a	36	34.97	8.286	34.48	38.57	
	3b	60	36.85	7.435	32.17	37.78	
	4	76	36.51	8.947	34.97	38.74	
	5	50	33.50	8.591	27.67	48.83	
VLDL	2	4	14.00	4.243	7.25	20.75	0.009
	3a	36	22.72	11.927	18.69	26.76	
	3b	60	23.26	9.975	20.72	25.79	
	4	76	24.62	11.301	22.06	27.19	
	5	50	29.50	14.109	25.49	33.51	

Above table demonstrated that mean changes of lipid profiles in relation to the CKD stages where it can easily distinguish that as the stages of CKD progresses there is increases of mean values of lipid profiles (TC, TG, LDL/VLDL) respectively except HDL which shows decrease in mean values with the progression of CKD stages and these changes found to be statistically significant with a p value mentioned in the respective parameters.

Figure 2: Relationship between Stage of CKD and lipid profile (N=226)

Discussion

In our study, most common lipid abnormalities found were Low HDL levels and Hypertriglyceridemia, Hypercholesterolemia, High LDL and VLDL levels were in decreasing order respectively.

Decreased High Density Lipoprotein Levels

In our study 190 patients were found to have low HDL level that is 84 % of total study population The mean HDL cholesterol is significantly decreased in the study group 35.73 ± 8.38 of Standard deviation and negative correlation is found between CKD stages and HDL level.

The low HDL levels in patients with chronic kidney disease in our study were consistent with Diana M Lee LG et al [13] who studied the lipid profile in CRF patients.

Elevated Triglycerides

70.3% of study populations were having high triglycerides levels. Mean and standard deviation of study population were 156.61 ± 31.65 . Demonstrates that CKD is commonly accompanied

by lipid abnormality in the form of hypertriglyceridemia. and positive correlation is found between CKD stages and triglycerides level.

Elevated Low Density Lipoprotein

101 patients was found to have elevated levels of LDL out of 226 patients which is 44.6% in our study. Mean and standard deviation of study population were 123.21 ± 23.31 . Positive correlation is found between CKD stages and LDL level.

Elevated Total Cholesterol

Total cholesterol levels were elevated in 100 patients in our study which is 44.2 % of total study population. Mean and standard deviation of study population were 195.93 ± 25.09 . This study shows positive correlation is found between CKD stages and TC level.

VLDL Level

VLDL levels were elevated in 36 patients in our study which is 15.9 % of total study population. Mean and standard deviation of study population were 24.83 ± 11.92 . This study shows positive

correlation is found between CKD stages and VLDL level.

Correlation Studies

The correlation between CKD stages and lipid profile parameters where TC TGL, LDL, and VLDL were showing positive correlation as CKD stages increases by 1 stage (from stage 2 to 3) there is increase of mean lipid profile values by 0.271 for TC, 0.189 for TGL, 0.192 for LDL, 0.215 for VLDL and where 0.098 decrease in HDL value suggestive of negative correlation of HDL with CKD stages and all the changes or differences in values found to be statistically significant with a p value of 0.000, 0.004, 0.004, 0.001 and 0.040 respectively.

ECG changes

In this study only 25.6% of ECG changes were seen normal in CKD patients. However, major changes seen as LVH (37.1%) followed by ischemic changes (18.58%) and tall T wave at V1-5 (8.8%). The risk of dying of cardiac complications is higher in CKD patients.

The risk factors which are responsible for increased morbidity and mortality were hypertension, DM, high LDL, low HDL and smoking.

Conclusion

1. HDL level was lower and Triglycerides, LDL, Total cholesterol and VLDL levels were higher in the study population.
2. Predominant lipid abnormalities were reduced HDL levels and elevated Triglycerides.
3. There is a statistically significant progressive increase in serum Triglycerides and reduced HDL level in patients with CKD stage 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively.
4. Triglycerides, LDL, Total Cholesterol and VLDL were showing positive correlation as CKD stages increases there is increase of mean lipid profile values.
5. There was a negative correlation between serum HDL level and GFR levels which was statistically significant.
6. Significant number of patients showing ECG changes of left ventricular hypertrophy 37.1% and ischemic changes 18.58% and tall T wave at V1-5 (8.8%)

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